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Metal-adducts of fullereneol-24 with some transition and rare earth metals

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Abstract:

The article describes the synthesis of fullerenol - $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ adducts with some heavy metals - $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$; $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$; me= Co; Cu; MN; Zn; Gd; Tb. The identification of adducts was carried out by the methods of: elemental analysis, infrared and electronic spectroscopy, complex thermal analysis, high-performance liquid chromatography and dynamic light scattering. The solubility of adducts in aqueous solutions in the natural temperature range has been studied. The use of these adducts as micronutrients for spring barley crops in the Republic of Kazakhstan is considered. When using these nano-preparations, a general increase in yield, nutrient content and moisture resistance of seeds, as well as the resistance of the latter to the effects of pathogenic microorganisms, was noted.

Keywords:

Adduct, fullerenol-24, transition metals, lanthanides, synthesis, identification, agrotechnical application, spring barley.

1. Introduction:

The paper describes the synthesis of fullerene-24 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ adducts with some transition metals and lanthanides: $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$; $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$; $Me = Co$; Cu ; Mn ; Zn ; Gd ; Tb . One of the possible and potential applications of fullerenols, considered in this work, is the synthesis of fullerene adducts with transition and 4f-metals, followed by the use of such adducts for agrochemical goals, as poorly soluble donors of micro-fertilizers of prolonged action, as well as agents that increase the nutrient content and moisture resistance of seeds, and also as well as the resistance of the latter to the effects of pathogenic microorganisms (on the example of spring barley). The most popular and available fullerene-24 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ was used for synthesis [1-3], the possible agrotechnical application of which (and some of its derivatives) was previously studied [3-8].

2. Synthesis of *Me*-adducts:

Synthesis of metal-adducts $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$; $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$; $Me = Co$; Cu ; Mn ; Zn ; Gd ; Tb was carried out in 2 stages:

The synthesis of Na-adducts:

The synthesis of *Me*-adducts themselves:

moreover, equation (2) corresponds to the synthesis of adducts with transients, and equation (3) corresponds to 4f-metals (lanthanides).

2.1. Synthesis scheme:

Dissolution 2.9 g. $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ in 30 cm³ 0.1 M NaOH solution, as a result, an aqueous solution $C_{60}(ONa)_{24}$ is formed. Bringing the pH of the solution to 7.5-8.5 a.u. with the addition of a few drops of 1 M solution of HCl.

Preparation of 100 cm³ of $MeCl_n$ solution ($Me = Co$; Cu ; Mn ; Zn ; Gd ; Tb) with a concentration of 55 g/dm³ ($CoCl_2$) ÷ 93 g/dm³ ($TbCl_3$) at a solution pH ~3.5÷4.0 a.u. in order to avoid hydrolysis of $MeCl_n$ (by adding a few drops of 1 M HCl solution).

Adding an aqueous solution of $MeCl_n$ drop by drop to an aqueous solution of $C_{60}(ONa)_{24}$. A loose amorphous colored precipitate is formed. Standing of the resulting solution with the formed precipitate for 24 hours. Filtration of the resulting heterogeneous mixture.

Three-time washing of the sediment with methanol CH_3OH for 50 cm³ of solvent. Final drying of adducts in a vacuum drying cabinet ($P \leq 0.1$ mm Hg) at a temperature of $\sim 50^\circ C$ for 90 min.

As a result, we synthesized gram amounts of colored crystal hydrates of Me -adducts: $C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6 \cdot 24H_2O$; $C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10} \cdot$

$18H_2O$; $C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10} \cdot 18H_2O$; $C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8 \cdot 20H_2O$; $C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6 \cdot 22H_2O$; $C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Tb)_6 \cdot 20H_2O$ with masses 3.8 g ($C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6 \cdot 24H_2O$) ÷ 4.1 g ($C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6 \cdot 22H_2O$), which corresponds to a practical yield of $\eta \sim 65-72\%$ of the theoretically possible.

Typical photos of synthesized adducts, shown in Fig. 1, were obtained using a VEGA 3 TESCAN electron microscope at magnification $\times 400 = \times 5000$.

It should be noted here that in acidic solutions, the formation of adducts of the type $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$; $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$ it is not observed in principle, which is unequivocally proved by analyzing solubility diagrams of the type: fullereneol-metal salt – water [2, 9-13].

3. Identification of Me -adducts:

Identification of Me -adducts: $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$; $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$; $Me = Co$; Cu ; Mn ; Zn ; Gd ; Tb was provided by the following methods of physico-chemical analysis:

IR spectra of adducts in KBr tablets were obtained on the Shimadzu FTIR-8400S spectrometer in the range of wave numbers $\tilde{\nu} = 400 \div 4000$ cm⁻¹;

Electronic absorption spectra were obtained on the SPECORD M32 spectrophotometer in the wavelength range $\lambda = 200 \div 1000$ nm (comparison solution – distilled water);

complex thermal analysis of adducts was carried out on a NETZSCH TG 209 F1 Libra analyzer in the temperature range of $30 \div 1100$ °C in an air atmosphere with a heating rate of $5K \cdot min^{-1}$;

For high-performance liquid chromatography, a Shimadzu LC-20 Prominence device with spectrophotometric detection at $\lambda = 270$ nm was used, equipped with a "Phenomenex®" column NH2" (150 mm × 2.0 mm, 5 microns, 100 Å), input volume $2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ cm³, input speed 0.2 ml·min⁻¹, eluent — acetonitrile/0.1% aqueous solution of acetic acid (5/95);

elemental composition analysis was carried out by scanning *VEGA 3 TESCAN* electron microscope in Essence software, using a fully integrated energy dispersion spectrometer (on a VEGA3 TESCAN electron microscope);

Additionally, elemental analysis for the sulfur content of light atoms was carried out using a *PerkinElmer PE 2400 CHN* analyzer;

Dynamic light scattering in aqueous solutions of adducts was carried out, using *Zetasizer Nano ZS*;

Solubility of adducts in aqueous solutions was studied using a standard shaker thermostat with additional temperature stabilization ($\Delta T = 0.05$ K, saturation time - 8 h, shaking frequency $\nu = 2$ Hz, solution concentrations were determined spectrophotometrically by absorption spectra at $\lambda = 270$ nm).

4. Elemental analysis:

The data of the elemental analysis are presented below in Table 1.

It is clearly seen that the composition of the precursor - $C_{60}(ONa)_{24} \cdot 24H_2O$ is set fairly accurately. Some variation in the content of *O* and *H* is associated with the presence of a large amount of loosely bound crystallization water in all adducts, while partial dehydration of equilibrium crystal-hydrates may occur on the surface of the crystal-hydrates (when studied in the atmosphere). For *Me*-adducts with transition metals and lanthanides – *Me*, the stability of the composition is significantly reduced, first of all, this applies to the content of *Me* in adducts. In our opinion, all adducts in the Table 1 can be considered mixtures of forms with slightly different compositions (related compounds) and their isomers. Indeed, the precursors used for the preparation of adducts are already primary, namely $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$, $C_{60}Br_{24}$ [3, 4, 14-16], are a mixture of isomers, not always strictly stoichiometric composition. Indeed, a halogen atom can be grafted into a pentagon-hexagonal *C* atom, into a hexagon-hexagonal *C* atom (then the structure will be inherited by fullerenol, its sodium forms and metalloadducts). Further, the substitution groups can alternatively be located: evenly distributed over the surface of the C_{60} core, mainly along the equator of the core, mainly circumpolarly, by spots, etc. Already during the formation of *Me*-adducts with two and three-charged cations, binding is possible with groups of one C_{60} fullerene core, two or even three different cows. Let's evaluate the possibilities of the last substitution. The average distance between neighboring substitution groups (*C-O-Na*) in the adduct $C_{60}(ONa)_{24}$ can be calculated in the simplest approximation of a uniform distribution of groups over the surface of the core: C_{60} : $r = (\pi d^2 / N)^{1/2}$, where: $d \sim 0.73$ nm – “diameter of fullerene core”, $N=24$. Or: $r \sim 0.26$ nm. The approximate length of

the sum of the bonds $r_{C-O-Na} \sim 0.3 \div 0.4 \text{ nm}$. In other words, taking into account the ionic radii Me^{z+} : $r_{Me^{z+}} \sim 0.073 (Cu) \div 0.092 (Tb) \text{ nm}$, it can be stated that geometrically binding of one multicharged ion can occur with either one or several fullerene cores. In the case of binding of one cation with several fullerene cores at once, the formation of more or less large oligomers should be revived. The formation of rather large associates (with linear dimensions of several microns) is further confirmed by the data of dynamic light scattering. On the other hand, according to the same reason, the electronic spectra of aqueous solutions of adducts will not be completely of the nature of light absorption, but at least partially of the nature of light scattering. In other words, the electronic spectra have a certain turbidimetric character.

5. Electronic spectroscopy:

Electronic spectroscopy data are represented in Fig.2, 3 and in Table 2. It is clearly visible, that the electronic absorption spectra of solutions of all *Me*-adducts are isomorphic: there are 2 broad absorption peaks at $\lambda_1 \sim 340 \div 360 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_2 \sim 265 \div 275 \text{ nm}$. According to the second peak, we further determined extinction coefficients and the volume concentrations of adducts:

$$D_{270} = \varepsilon_{270} C \left(\frac{g}{dm^3} \right) l(cm) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

$$C \left(\frac{g}{dm^3} \right) = D_{270} / \varepsilon_{270} l(cm) = \kappa_{270} D_{270} / l \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where: *l* – width of the cuvette (length of optical way);

ε_{270} - extinction coefficients in the Booger - Lambert - Behr law at wavelength $\lambda=270 \text{ nm}$;

C – volume concentration in $\frac{g}{dm^3}$;

D_{270} – optical density;

κ_{270} - coefficients for concentration recalculation.

5.1. Infrared spectroscopy:

The absorption *IR* spectra of all *Me*-adducts also turned out to be isomorphic. All of them present: vibrations of the fullerene core C_{60} : $\bar{\nu} (cm^{-1}) = 528 \div 532$; $570 \div 577$; $1170 \div 1183$; $1423 \div 1429$; vibrations of H_2O crystal-hydrate molecules: $\bar{\nu} (cm^{-1}) = 3595 \div 3620$; $3448 \div 3454$; $1640 \div 1651$; relatively weak fluctuations of residual and hydrolyzed *O-H* groups: $\bar{\nu} (cm^{-1}) = 3417 \div 3421$; vibrations of *C-O* groups: $\bar{\nu} (cm^{-1}) = 1716 \div 1728$; vibrations of *O-Na* groups: $\bar{\nu} (cm^{-1}) = 540 \div 565$; the system of peaks, corresponding to the vibrations of *Me-O*, *O-Me-O*: $\bar{\nu} (cm^{-1}) = 424 (Zn) \div 599 (Tb)$.

5.2. Complex thermal analysis:

Complex thermal analysis of crystal-hydrates was carried out for the following crystal-hydrates of metal products: $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2} \cdot NH_2O$ и $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me')_{(24-x)/3} \cdot N'H_2O$ ($Me = Co, Cu, Mn, Zn; Me' = Gd, Tb$). Let's denote: $T^{(start)} \rightarrow T^{(ext)} \rightarrow T^{(fin)}$ - temperatures of the beginning, extreme and end of the effect. We denote the following processes: *MED* – multistage dehydration of crystallohydrates; *T-RE-OMD* – decomposition with the release of *Me* oxide; *SOD* – decomposition with the release of Na_2O oxide; *FCO* – additional oxidation of fullerene core. In all cases, the effects were consistently observed on the thermograms: *MED* \rightarrow *T-RE-OMD* \rightarrow *SOD* \rightarrow *FCO* - (see Table. 3).

5.3. High performance liquid phase chromatography (HPLC):

Typical example of a chromatogram of *Me*-adduct - $C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$ is represented in Fig.4. It is clearly seen from the figure that the mixture of adducts leaves the chromatographic column with a relatively wide peak (with base ~ 2 min and half-width ~ 1 min), which indirectly indicates the formation of a group of izomers of closely related compounds of very similar composition. Before entering the column, the adduct solution was centrifuged to separate the largest associates with linear dimensions of several microns.

5.4. Solubility in water solutions in natural range of temperatures:

Solubility of *Me*-adducts in water solutions in natural range of temperatures are represented in Table 4 and Fig.5. Solubility data confirmed, that the solubility of all crystal hydrates of adducts is quite significant for feeding the root system of cereals and amounts to $0.3 \div 1.1$ g/dm³. On the other hand, solubility is not too big for too much rapid dissolution and exhaustion of microelements in soils. Fig.5 also shows, that the solubility of all *Me*-adducts (without changing the type of crystal-hydrate) increases with decreasing temperature, which can be very valuable from an agrotechnical point of view, since the maximum supply of plants with trace elements will be observed precisely at temperatures around 0 ° C (during melting or the first snowfall in the spring-autumn period), when these elements are maximally they are in demand for the development of cereals.

5.5. Dynamic light scattering in water solutions:

All solutions of *Me*-adducts in water turned out to be hierarchically associated in a complex way. Consistent formation of I-order associates with typical linear dimensions was observed in them δ_I in tens of nm, II order (δ_{II} of the order of 100 nm); III order (δ_{III} of the order of several

microns), and the formation of the latter corresponds to a microheterogenic solution. Unassociated metalloadducts ($\delta_0 \sim 2$ nm were not observed by us). Typical examples of particle size distribution are shown in Table 5 and Fig. 6.

Elementary calculation (in spherical approximation) allows us to calculate the number of monomeric *Me*-adduct molecules in the *i*-th order associate - N_{i-0} (Table 5):

$$N_{i-0} = (\delta_i/\delta_0)^3 \cdot K_{pack}^i; N_{i+1-i} = (\delta_{i+1}/\delta_i)^3 \cdot K_{pack}; K_{pack} = \pi/6 \quad \dots\dots (6)$$

where: (K_{pack} – packing coefficient of “small spheres into a large sphere”).

Also one can calculate the number of *i*-th order associates of *Me*-adduct in the (*i+1*)-th order associate - N_{i+1-i} (Table 5):

$$N_{i+1-i} = (\delta_{i+1}/\delta_i)^3 \cdot K_{pack} \quad \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

For these calculations one should estimate dimensions of hydrated monomers - δ_0 also in spherical approximation:

$$\delta_0 = \delta(C_{60}) + 2r(C - O) + 2r(O - Me) + 2\delta(H_2O) \approx 0.73 + 2 \cdot 0.14 + 2(0.22 \div 0.33) + 2 \cdot 0.3 \approx 2 \text{ nm} \quad \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

The 3-order associates undoubtedly correspond to the micro-heterogenic colloidal state of the solutions. In the Table 5 are also represented electro-kinetic ξ –potentials and mobilities of different order associates of *Me*-adducts. The negative potential of all associates, on the one hand, determines the sedimentation stability of solutions, and, on the other hand, prevent further enlargement of associates of the III order. The latter were isolated, deposited on a quartz substrate and photographed by us *VEGA 3 TESCAN* electron microscope (Fig.7). It follows from the obtained data that the main carriers of *Me*-adducts are probably associates of the second order, since there are relatively many of them in solution, and their mobility in solution is maximal. We did not find unassociated molecules of *Me*-adducts in solution even at the lowest concentrations ($C = 0.01 \text{ g/dm}^3$) and we cannot assume their existence in real aqueous solutions.

5.6. The effect of micro-fertilizers based on *Me*-adducts on the yield of spring barley:

In terms of grain exports, Kazakhstan ranks 9-th in the world (5 million tons). The dominant part in grain production is wheat and barley [17]. Studies of the obtained samples of *Me*-adducts were carried out from May to October 2022 on experimental fields of peasant farms located in the East of Kazakhstan (Figure 8). The object of research is spring barley on non-irrigated (rainfed) and irrigated plots. The object of research is spring barley in non-irrigated (rainfed) and irrigated plots. The type of soil, the humus content in it and the main agro-climatic

indicators according to Kazhydromet and the weather station for 2022 are presented in Table 6.

In previous experiments, the consumption of fullerenols and *Me*-adducts, amounting to $Con \sim 12.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2$, was preliminarily determined. Introduction of fullerenols and *Me*-adducts was carried out in the form of water solutions of fullerenols and *Me*-adducts with the concentration $C = 10 \text{ mg}/\text{dm}^3$). For the effective treatment of spring barley with *Me*-adducts it was necessary to ensure the uniformity of the soil at the experimental site, which can be very difficult. An increase in the size of the plot often leads to an increase in the total area of the experiment and the probability of going beyond the uniformity increases. Based on long-term practice [18], it is advisable to set the area of the field experiment plot within 100 m^2 , with a 4-fold repetition of options. Table 7 shows abbreviated names of fullerenols and *Me*-adducts in the field experiment, used later in the report. Relatively cheap and more affordable mixed fullereneol-d [19, 20] - $C_{60}O_x(OH)_{18 \div 30}$, was used by us for comparison.

Processing of barley crops was carried out twice in the tillering – tube phase with an interval of 7 days. In variants with non-root treatment with solutions of water-soluble fullerenes - individual fullereneol-24 and mixed fullereneol-d, barley crops were sprayed twice in the tillering phase - the beginning of the exit into the tube. Barley crops not treated with fullereneols solutions were used as a control sample.

In variants with root treatment with solutions of water-soluble *Me*-adducts with copper, manganese, cobalt and zinc, barley crops were also treated twice in the tillering phase - the beginning of the exit into the tube. As a control sample, barley crops not treated with solutions of the above fullerenols were used. The treatment was carried out by spraying spring barley from a hand sprayer. The dates of treatment of spring barley crops with fullerenols and *Me*-adducts are given in Table 8.

To determine the biological yield of grain crops at each experimental landfill of all three polygons a sample was taken from an area $S = 1.0 \text{ m}^2$.

For this purpose, a special frame made of thin but strong slats (a meter frame) was used. The side of the frame in the internal measurement was equal to one meter. To make it easier to apply the frame for sampling, three of its sides are fixed tightly, and the fourth is freely removed and laid. The material was selected from 5 points of the test site of the landfill in accordance with the methodology for organizing and conducting a survey of grain yields [18].

The positive effect of the studied nanopreparations – fullerenols and *Me*-adducts on the yield of spring barley at all the studied polygons was noted. The increase in yield during the processing of experimental plots in comparison with the control samples is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 10 shows the effect of fullerene type on spring barley yield in rainfed (red, Polygon III-a) and irrigated (blue, Polygon-III) plots. Field studies to assess the effect of nanopreparations on the yield of spring barley have shown the following.

This is confirmed by previous studies aimed at increasing the productivity and sustainability of crops, especially under stressful conditions - moisture deficiency [8], [21]. There was practically no positive effect of individual fullerene – 24 and fullerene – d when spraying spring barley crops at Polygon III-a. The effect of nanopreparations was most strongly manifested on the non-irrigated areas of landfill III-a in variants with root treatment with solutions of water-soluble fullerenes - fullerene adducts with copper, manganese, cobalt and zinc, where the yield of spring barley increased by 54-80 rel. %. On the irrigation experimental plots of the same farm (polygon III), the effect of fullerenols was manifested both during spraying and during root treatment. In the case of spraying with solutions of fullerene – 24 and fullerene – d, an increase in the yield of spring barley was observed by 23 – 29 rel. %. Basal treatment with *Me*-adducts with copper, manganese, cobalt and zinc showed a greater increase in the yield of spring barley by 34-45 rel.%.

Significantly less than expected, the effect of fullerene and *Me*-adducts was manifested in Polygon I and Polygon II. When spraying crops at Polygon I with solutions of fullerene – 24 and fullerene – d, an increase in the yield of spring barley was observed from 2.5 to 21 rel.%. Basal treatment of crops with *Me*-adducts with copper, manganese, cobalt and zinc at the same landfill showed better results - an increase in the yield of spring barley was in the range of 25 – 41 rel.%. When spraying crops at landfill II with solutions of fullerene – 24 and fullerene – d, the increase in the yield of spring barley was in the range of 3-7 rel.%. The root treatment of crops with *Me*-adducts with copper, manganese, cobalt and zinc at the same landfill showed an increase in the yield of spring barley from 7 to 21 rel.%.

The positive effect of water-soluble derivatives of fullerenes derivatives – fullereneols and complex ethers of C_{60} with amino-acids in the cultivation of agricultural crops is confirmed by many authors – see, for example [17, 22-24]. A number of researchers have found that fullereneols (and its derivatives) have antibacterial and antiviral activity, as well as antioxidant properties in their interaction with microorganisms and biological objects of animal origin [21, 25-28]. In the review presented in [25], the synthesis of fullereneols is described and several mechanisms of antioxidant activity of fullereneol are proposed. The antioxidant activity of fullereneols indicates the possibility of using these nanomaterials in crop production to increase the productivity and stability of crops, especially under stressful conditions [7]. One of the main stress factors in the cultivation of agricultural crops is a lack of moisture. If regenerative

processes develop in normally moistened soil, then in conditions of lack of water - oxidative, which leads to the suspension of the plant growth process. Fullerenols and derivatives have the ability to bind reactive oxygen species, so we can expect from them a positive effect on the process of ammonification-nitrification and, as a consequence, a decrease in the amount of nitrogen fertilizers applied [6], [7], [29]. Thus, the authors believe, that they can confidently assert, that the use of fullerenols and derivatives helps to increase yields by stimulating water retention and combating certain pathogens [24]. Also, some research presented in the paper [18, 30, 31] It has been shown, that fullereneol regulates oxidative stress and homeostasis of tissue ions in spring wheat, improving net primary productivity under salt stress.

5.7. Quality control of seeds, processed by fullerenols and *Me*-adducts:

Quality control of spring barley, seeds processed by fullerenols and *Me*-adducts during the ripening period was carried out according to the main indicators, according to the State Standard of Russia. The impact of fullerenols and *Me*-adducts seeds was carried out according to the methodology, described in the previous section “The effect of micro-fertilizers based on *Me*-adducts on the yield of spring barley” in the same times and concentrations. For the experiments, barley seeds obtained from the irrigated Polygon III were used. Control seeds samples were not treated by fullerenols and *Me*-adducts during the ripening period. The abbreviated name of fullereneol and *Me-adduct* in the experiment are saved from the Table 7. Following seeds quality characteristics were controlled: seed grade purity; weight of 1000 seeds; moisture content in seeds; laboratory germination of seeds; seed germination energy [32-37].

Seed grade purity is the weight amount of pure seeds of the studied breed, expressed as a percentage of the total weight of seeds in the batch together with waste and impurities;

The mass of 1000 seeds is an indicator of the size and maturation of 1000 units of dry grains, expressed in grams;

Moisture content is the content of hygroscopic water in the seeds or the percentage of water in the seed sample at the time of their selection;

Laboratory germination was determined on the 10-th day, during the analysis as the proportion of germinated seeds, expressed in relative terms %;

Seed germination energy was determined on the 10-th day, during the analysis as the proportion of germinated seeds, expressed in relative terms %.

The results are represented in the Table. 9 and Fig.11.

Conclusions on the section.

1. The purest sample of spring barley seed material is a sample obtained from plants, treated with a fullereneol adduct with manganese (*Mn*-adduct). This sample is the only sample that surpasses the control sample in varietal purity. The remaining samples in varietal purity are either very slightly inferior to the control, or correspond to it.
2. The mass of 1000 grains of spring barley obtained from plants treated with fullereneols and *Me*-adducts is significantly higher compared to the control sample. The highest value of this indicator is observed in seeds obtained from plants treated with *Cu*-adduct.
3. The moisture content of spring barley seeds allows the storage of this cereal for a sufficiently long time without loss of grain quality. Most of the samples from plants treated fullereneols and *Me*-adducts, compared with the control sample, showed a higher water content in the seed structure.
4. The highest laboratory germination rates are observed in spring barley seeds, from plants treated *Zn*-adduct and fullereneol – d. The minimum values of laboratory germination in the sample after treatment with *Co*-adduct.
5. Practically all samples of spring barley seeds have a significant decrease in the percentage of laboratory germination compared to the germination energy. This may be due to the defeat of seeds by pathogenic microorganisms and, subsequently, their death. The only sample of spring barley seed material, in which the value of germination energy and laboratory germination are at the same level, is a sample of seeds from plants treated with *Zn*-adduct. This fact may be related to the acquired resistance of the seed material to the effects of pathogenic microorganisms.

5.8. Infection of seeds, processed by fullereneols and *Me*-adducts, with pathogenic microorganisms:

Phytopathological examination includes germination of seeds by the "roll method" and, after 12-14 days, accounting and identification of the species composition of pathogenic microorganisms by microscopy. Looking at the seedlings under the BX-51 optical research microscope (OLYMPUS, Japan), the presence and type of pathogen were noted. When taking into account diseases, index was determined: the proportion of seeds affected by this pathogen (in relative percentages).

Infected seed material can lead to significant crop losses and a decrease in grain quality. Seeds infected with dusty smut of wheat and barley have reduced germination. Fusarium infections, helminthosporiotic root rot, bacterioses can lead to death or damage to the root system of seedlings, which is the cause of thinning of crops. Saprotrophic mold fungi of such genera as *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Mucor*, *Rhizopus*, *Cladosporium*, *Epicoccum*, do not allow young

shoots to develop normally and lead to their death. Dusty and hard smut of cereals, fusarium root rot are the reason for the reduction of productive stems [38].

In Fig.12 we demonstrate typical photos of the most popular infections for spring barley seeds identified by us: *Helminthosporiosis - Bipolaris Sorokiniana*; *Fusarium - Fusarium sp.*; *Saprotrophic mold fungi – genus: Rhizopus; Mucor; Aspergillus*. The results of determining the infestation of spring barley seeds with pathogenic microorganisms, obtained from plants treated with fullerenols and *Me*-adducts, as well as in a control sample, are shown in Table 10 and Fig13.

6. Conclusions on the section:

1. *Helminthosporiosis (Bipolaris Sorokiniana)* was observed in all samples of spring barley. At the same time, minimal paralysis was observed in the control samples. During the analysis, a color change to black was noted at the embryonic end of the seed. Helminthosporiosis spores are shown in Figure 12.
2. *Fusarium sp.* was observed only in a sample of spring barley from plants treated Co-adducts. A diagnostic sign of *Fusarium* seedlings is dark necrosis on the roots and stems. The development of *Fusarium* on seedlings leads to the death of plants. During phytopathological examination, there is a pink plaque on the filter paper, which is left by fusariotoxins.
3. Compared with the control samples of spring barley, the indicators of infection with fungal infestation of seeds from plants, treated with fullerenols and *Me*-adducts are significantly lower. This fact may indicate the effectiveness of the protection of fullerene *Me*-adducts from such infections - *Saprotrophic mold fungi* with determined genus: *Rhizopus; Mucor; Aspergillus*. The best and almost identical result was obtained, when using all *Me*-adducts.
4. Percentage of healthy seeds (magenta) in general is better for *Me*-adducts than control samples, and the best result is for *Zn*-adduct, and the worst one – for *Mn*-adduct.

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8. Literature:

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Tables for the article N.A.Kulenova and co “Possible Agrotechnical Application:

Table. 1: Elemental composition of Me-adducts: $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$, $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$

№	Me in adduct	Element atomic content per q fullerene core (C ₆₀) (60 C atoms).					Me-adducts formula
		C	O	H	Na	Me	
1	Na	60	44±2	40±2	24±1	0	C ₆₀ (ONa) ₂₄ · 20H ₂ O
2	Co	60	48±6	48±5	12±3	6±2	C ₆₀ (ONa) ₁₂ (O ₂ Co) ₆ · 24H ₂ O
3	Cu	60	42±8	36±5	4±2	10±4	C ₆₀ (ONa) ₄ (O ₂ Cu) ₁₀ · 18H ₂ O
4	Mn	60	42±9	36±4	4±2	10±5	C ₆₀ (ONa) ₄ (O ₂ Mn) ₁₀ · 18H ₂ O
5	Zn	60	44±7	40±5	8±3	8±3	C ₆₀ (ONa) ₈ (O ₂ Zn) ₈ · 20H ₂ O
6	Gd	60	46±8	44±6	6±3	6±3	C ₆₀ (ONa) ₆ (O ₃ Gd) ₆ · 22H ₂ O
7	Tb	60	44±8	40±7	6±3	6±3	C ₆₀ (ONa) ₆ (O ₂ Tb) ₆ · 20H ₂ O

Table. 2: Extinction coefficients in the Booger - Lambert - Behr law and coefficients for concentration recalculation at wavelength $\lambda=270$ nm in Me-adduct water solutions.

Num	Me in the adduct	Extinction coefficients	Coefficients for volume concentration calculations
	$C_{60}(OH)_{24-n}(O_nMe_{n/x})$	ϵ_{270} (10 ³ cm ² /g)	κ_{270} (g/dm ³)

1	Co	0.915	1.093
2	Cu	0.572	1.748
3	Mn	0.850	1.176
4	Zn	0.391	2.557
5	Gd	0.568	1.760
6	Tb	0.733	1.364

**Table 3: Complex thermal analysis of crystal-hydrates of metal-adducts of fullerene-24 with metals: $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2} \cdot NH_2O$ and $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me')_{(24-x)/3} \cdot N'H_2O$ ($Me = Co, Cu, Mn, Zn;$
 $Me'=Gd, Tb$).**

Num	Process	Temperature (C): $T^{(start)} \rightarrow T^{(ext)} \rightarrow T^{(fin)}$
1.	$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6 \cdot 24H_2O \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6 + 24H_2O - MED$	75 \rightarrow 300 \rightarrow 340
2.	$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 6CoO + C_{60}(ONa)_{12}O_6 - T-RE-OMD$	350 \rightarrow 405 \rightarrow 500
3.	$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}O_6 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}O_{12} + 6Na_2O - SOD$	500 \rightarrow 575 \rightarrow 645
4.	$C_{60}O_{12} + 54O_2 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 60 CO_2 - FCO$	680 \rightarrow 1000 \rightarrow ...
5.	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10} \cdot 18H_2O \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}(ONa)_2(O_2Cu)_{10} + 18H_2O - MED$	70 \rightarrow 285 \rightarrow 330
6.	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10} \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 10CuO + C_{60}(ONa)_4O_{10} - T-RE-OMD$	330 \rightarrow 390 \rightarrow 485
7.	$C_{60}(ONa)_4O_{10} \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}O_{12} + 2Na_2O - SOD$	490 \rightarrow 565 \rightarrow 640

8.	$C_{60}O_{12} + 54O_2 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 60 CO_2 - FCO$	680 → 1000 → ...
9.	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10} \cdot 18H_2O \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}(ONa)_2(O_2Mn)_{10} \cdot 18H_2O - MED$	80 → 310 → 355
10.	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10} \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 10MnO + C_{60}(ONa)_4O_{10} - T-RE-OMD$	345 → 395 → 505
11.	$C_{60}(ONa)_4O_{10} \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}O_{12} + 2Na_2O - SOD$	510 → 585 → 660
12.	$C_{60}O_{12} + 54O_2 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 60 CO_2 - FCO$	680 → 1000 → ...
13.	$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8 \cdot 20H_2O \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8 \cdot 20H_2O - MED$	95 → 315 → 360
14.	$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 8ZnO + C_{60}(ONa)_8O_8 - T-RE-OMD$	355 → 430 → 510
15.	$C_{60}(ONa)_8O_8 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}O_{12} + 4Na_2O - SOD$	515 → 590 → 665
16.	$C_{60}O_{12} + 54O_2 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 60 CO_2 - FCO$	680 → 1000 → ...
17.	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6 \cdot 22H_2O \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6 \cdot 22H_2O - MED$	90 → 320 → 365
18.	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 3Gd_2O_3 + C_{60}(ONa)_6O_9 - T-RE-OMD$	385 → 470 → 530
19.	$C_{60}(ONa)_6O_9 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}O_{12} + 3Na_2O - SOD$	540 → 610 → 680
20.	$C_{60}O_{12} + 54O_2 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 60 CO_2 - FCO$	680→1000→...

21.	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Tb)_6 \cdot 20H_2O \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Tb)_6 \cdot 20H_2O - MED$	90 → 325 → 370
22.	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Tb)_6 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 3Tb_2O_3 + C_{60}(ONa)_6O_9 - T-RE-OMD$	375 → 465 → 540
23.	$C_{60}(ONa)_6O_9 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow C_{60}O_{12} + 3Na_2O - SOD$	545 → 615 → 685
24.	$C_{60}O_{12} + 54O_2 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow 60 CO_2 - FCO$	680 → 1000 → ...

Table 4. Solubility in the systems: $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$ or $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3} - H_2O$; Me: Co; Cu; Mn; Zn; Gd; Tb.

Num	System	Crystal hydrate	Temperature (°C)	Solubility S(g/dm ³)
1	$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6$ $- H_2O$	$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6 \cdot 24H_2O$	25	0.340
2			0	0.419
3	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10}$ $- H_2O$	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10} \cdot 18H_2O$	25	0.503
4			0	0.636
5	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10}$ $- H_2O$	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10} \cdot 18H_2O$	25	0.444
6			0	0.665
7	$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$ $- H_2O$	$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8 \cdot 20H_2O$	25	0.634
8			0	1.041
9	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6$ $- H_2O$	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6 \cdot 22H_2O$	25	0.552
10			0	0.627
11	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_2Tb)_6$ $- H_2O$	$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Tb)_6 \cdot 20H_2O$	25	0.492
12			0	0.521

Table. 5: Size distribution, electro-kinetic ξ –potentials and mobility of the associates of Me-adducts of fulleranol-24 with some metals:

<i>Me</i> -adduct	Concentration C(g/dm ³)	δ_0 (nm)	δ_I (nm)	δ_{II} (nm)	δ_{III} (μ m)	
$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6$	0.34	-	65	105	7	
$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10}$	0.55	-	-	105	5	
$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10}$	0.49	-	-	108	5	
$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$	0.88	-	-	120	5	
$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6$	0.72	-	-	120	6	
$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_2Tb)_6$	0.50	-	65	103	7	
<i>Me</i> -adduct	N_{I-0} (a. u.)	N_{II-0} (a. u.)	N_{III-0} (a. u.)	N_{II-I} (a. u.)	N_{III-I} (a. u.)	N_{III-II} (a. u.)
$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6$	$2 \cdot 10^4$	$3 \cdot 10^4$	$4 \cdot 10^9$	2	$3 \cdot 10^5$	$1 \cdot 10^5$
$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10}$	-	$3 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^9$	2	$1 \cdot 10^5$	$5 \cdot 10^4$
$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10}$	-	$3 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^9$	2	$1 \cdot 10^5$	$5 \cdot 10^4$
$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$	-	$4 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^9$	3	$1 \cdot 10^5$	$4 \cdot 10^4$
$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6$	-	$4 \cdot 10^4$	$3 \cdot 10^9$	3	$2 \cdot 10^5$	$6 \cdot 10^4$
$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_2Tb)_6$	$2 \cdot 10^4$	$3 \cdot 10^4$	$4 \cdot 10^9$	2	$3 \cdot 10^5$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
<i>Me</i> -adduct	ξ_I (mV)	ξ_{II} (mV)	ξ_{III} (mV)	U_I (μ m·cm/V·s)	U_{II} (μ m·cm/V·s)	U_{III} (μ m·cm/V·s)
$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6$	-20	-35	-60	-1.4	-1.8	-0.5
$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10}$	-	-35	-50	-	-2.1	-0.7
$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10}$	-	-35	-50	-	-2.0	-0.7
$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$	-	-40	-50	-	-2.3	-0.7

$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6$	-	-40	-55	-	-2.4	-0.6
$C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_2Tb)_6$	-20	-30	-60	-1.5	-2.1	-0.5

Table. 6: Main agro-climatic indicators during the period of research in various farms (June - September 2022)

The name of the indicator	Polygon-I	Polygon-II	Polygon-III
Soil type	Ordinary chernozem, leached, of medium mechanical composition	Dark brown, light mechanical composition, subject to water and wind erosion	Chestnut, light mechanical composition, highly susceptible to water and wind erosion
Humus content, %	4.1 ÷ 5.3	1.0 ÷ 1.6	0.6 ÷ 1.3
The amount of precipitation for the entire growing season, mm	182	123	136
Average temperature for the entire growing season, °C	23.5	18.1	21.2

Table. 7: Abbreviated name of the corresponding fulleranol and Me-adduct in the field experiment:

The abbreviated name of fulleranol and Me-adduct in the field experiment	full name of fulleranol and Me-adducts
C	Control (without processing)
F1	Fullerenol-24 – $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$
F2	Fullerenol-d [19, 20]
F3	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10}$

F4	$C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10}$
F5	$C_{60}(ONa)_{12}(O_2Co)_6$
F6	$C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$

Table.8: Dates of sowing and processing of spring barley in experimental farms with various types of fullerenols and Me-adducts.

	Date of sowing of spring barley	Data of the first treatment by fullerenols and Me-adducts	Data of the second treatment by fullerenols and Me-adducts
Polygon I	05.05.2022	08.06.2022	15.06.2022
Polygon II	12.05.2022	16.06.2022	23.06.2022
Polygon III	26.05.2022	29.06.2022	06.07.2022
Polygon III-a	26.05.2022	29.06.2022	06.07.2022

Table. 9: Quality control of seeds, processed by fullerenols and Me-adducts.

fullerenol and Me-adduct	Seed grade purity (rel. %)	weight of 1000 seeds (g)	Moisture content in seeds (rel. mass. %)	Laboratory germination of seeds (rel. %)	Seed germination energy (rel. %)
C	95.5	39.2	4.14	87.5	100.0
F1	93.9	41.2	4.31	87.5	97.5
F2	94.8	44.2	4.36	90.0	100,0.
F3	95.4	46.4	4.74	87.5	97.5
F4	97.5	42.6.	4.62	87.5	97.5
F5	95.3	41.7	4.07	80.0	92.5
F6	95.0	42.2	4.75	92.5	92.5

Table. 10: Results of determination of infestation of spring barley seeds with pathogenic microorganisms.

Fullerenol and Me-adduct	Detected pathogens, rel. %		Mold and spots, rel. %	Healthy seeds*, rel. %
	Helminthosporiosis	Fusariosis		
C	2.5	0.0	20.0	77.5
F1	5.0	0.0	10.0	85.0
F2	17.5	0.0	5.0	77.5
F3	10.0	0.0	5.0	85.0
F4	12.5	0.0	5.0	82.5
F5	10.0	4.0	5.0	85.0
F6	7.5	0.0	5.0	87.5

*Taking into account *Helminthosporiosis*; *Fusariosis*; *Mold and spots* infestation only.

Figures for the article N.A.Kulenova and co “Possible Agrotechnical Application...”

Figure. 1: Electronic photos of the crystalline Me-adducts $C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10} \cdot 18H_2O$ (*5000 – on the left, on the scale is represented by the photos), $C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Gd)_6 \cdot 22H_2O$ (*500 center), $C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8 \cdot 20H_2O$ (*400 – right).

Figure. 2: Electronic spectra of water solutions of the Me-adducts:

$C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$ or $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$ against distilled water; Me: Co (black); Cu (red); Mn (blue); Zn (magenta); Gd (green); Tb (cyan); at cuvette width $l=10$ cm. Solution concentrations in g/dm^3 : Co (0.040); Cu (0.043); Mn (0.040); Zn (0.043); Gd (0.037); Tb (0.040).

Figure. 3: Booger - Lambert - Behr law validness in the electronic spectra of water solutions of the Me-adducts:

$C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_2Me)_{(24-x)/2}$ or $C_{60}(ONa)_x(O_3Me)_{(24-x)/3}$ against distilled water; Me: Co (black); Cu (red); Mn (blue); Zn (magenta); Gd (green); Tb (cyan); at cuvette width $l=10$ cm.

Figure. 4: Example of a chromatogram of Me-adduct - $C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$.

Figure. 5. Solubility of Me-adducts in water solutions in natural range of temperatures Me: Co (black); Cu (red); Mn (blue); Zn (magenta); Gd (green); Tb (cyan).

Figure. 6: Size distribution of the associates of metal-adducts of fullereneol-24 with some metals: $C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$ (top); $C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10}$ (middle); $C_{60}(ONa)_6(O_3Tb)_6$ (bottom).

Figure. 7: Electronic photos of III-order associates of metal-adducts of fulleranol-24 with some metals: $C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Cu)_{10}$ (top); $C_{60}(ONa)_4(O_2Mn)_{10}$ (middle); $C_{60}(ONa)_8(O_2Zn)_8$ (bottom). Average “diameter” of associates is $\approx 5\div 7 \mu m$ (examples).

Figure. 8: Location of experimental farms on the map Kazakhstan

Figure. 9: Increase in the yield of spring barley compared to control (red - Polygon I; blue - Polygon II; green - Polygon III; magenta - Polygon III-a)

Figure. 10: Dependence of the effect of the fullereneol and Me-adduct type on the yield of spring barley on rain-fed (red, Polygon III-a) and irrigated (blue, Polygon-III) plots

Figure. 11: Quality control of seeds, processed by fullereneols and Me-adducts: seed grade purity (red); weight of 1000 seeds*2.5 (magenta); moisture content in seeds *25 (cyan); laboratory germination of seeds (blue); seed germination energy (green).

Figure. 12. Typical photos of the most popular infections for spring barley seeds identified by authors: *Helminthosporiosis - Bipolaris Sorokiniana* (top-left; top-right); *Fusarium - Fusarium sp* (middle-left); *Saprotrrophic mold fungi – genus: Rhizopus*(middle-right); *Mucor* (bottom-left); *Aspergillus* (bootom-right). **Magnification scales in µm are represented in the photos.**

Figure. 13. Results of determination of infestation of spring barley seeds with pathogenic microorganisms, taking into account *Helminthosporiosis* (red); *Fusariosis* (blue); *Mold and spots* (green) infestation and percentage of healthy seeds (magenta)